

FORMATION OF SPEECH-THINKING ACTIVITY OF PRESCHOOLERS WITH GENERAL SPEECH UNDERDEVELOPMENT

Bakirova Umida Bakhtiyor kizi

Gulistan State University Faculty of Pedagogy 3rd year student

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Preschool age is a period when children begin to develop systemic ideas about the world around them, which contributes to the formation of a child's needs for communication and cognition. The activation of the child's communicative and speech sphere creates the necessary conditions for full-fledged life activity, the development of his abilities, successful mastery of household, educational, gaming skills and abilities. Successful social adaptation of a child depends on the level of formation of speech-thinking operations that ensure the deployment of thought in external speech. The development of speech-thinking activity is an important task of preparing preschoolers for school. Nevertheless, the field of research of speech-thinking activity is still among the poorly developed.

The process of speech formation at preschool age is closely related to the intellectual development of the child, with the emergence of various types of thinking, the expansion of ideas about the world around. Fundamental studies of L.S. Vygotsky, A.R. Luria, J. Piaget and others are devoted to the study of the relationship between thinking and speech in ontogenesis. According to A.A. Leontiev, "a person has nothing to do with one speech: it is not an end in itself, but a means, a tool, although it can be used in different ways in different types of activities". That is, there is not a speech activity as such, but a system of speech actions included in some kind of activity - entirely theoretical, intellectual or practical.

The peculiarity of speech-thinking activity, as shown in the works of P.M. Alekseev, N.P. Antonov, L.S. Vygotsky, I.N. Gorelov, N.P. Erastov, A.R. Luria, S.I. Lvova, A.A. Lyublinskaya, S.L. Rubinstein, I.V. Sorokina, A.G. Spirkin and others, is its reflective and transformative character. Thanks to this type of activity, the child perceives, rethinks and restructures information in order to then use it again in speech.

Speech-thinking activity is fully possible only under the condition of normal development of speech and thinking. In children with ONR, all components of the speech system are disrupted and there are some disorders of mental processes: perception, attention, memory, thinking, analytical activity, logical operations, representations, etc.

In this regard, much attention is paid to finding ways to develop speech in parallel with the activation of mental activity. Comparing the process of nutting with the process of performing mental operations, we need to uncover those cognitive prerequisites that allow us to identify the level of language acquisition and develop methods of corrective action for further language acquisition by children with general speech underdevelopment. This was our main task, the solution of which was devoted to experimental research. 24 preschool children with ONR took part in the experiment. The research methodology included 3 series of tasks.

The experimental tasks of the 1st series were based on visual material and allowed to get an idea of the non-speech processes of the child. The children were asked to complete the following tasks: to identify an extra picture in a series of thematic pictures; to highlight minor differences in the images of the same object when examining two pictures sequentially; to choose two identical images when considering several identical ones; to guess objects by their details.

Analyzing the results of this experiment, it can be said that children with ONR have a reduced ability to generalize and analyze visual material, perception of the integrity of the object; there is insufficient formation of the ability to abstract, highlight common properties of objects, visually comparing them.

2 a series of experimental tasks assessed the state of the lexical and grammatical structure of children's speech and was based on words, sentences, texts. It included tests for comparing two subjects; verification of sentences; making sentences from words in the initial form; addition of sentences with omitted prepositions; understanding of complex logical and grammatical constructions; understanding of the text read.

Taking into account the quality of children's responses, it can be concluded that older preschoolers with ONR have reduced critical thinking, attention, and the ability to correlate what they have heard with adequate reality. They have a poor command of the ability to justify their judgments.

3 a series of experimental tasks tested the formation of phonemic analysis and synthesis in children at the level of the sound composition of words. It consisted of tests to determine the vowel (consonant) sound at the beginning, middle and end of a word; to compose a word from syllables. The performance of tasks in this series showed that older preschoolers with ONR have a low level of phonemic perception and sound analysis and synthesis.

According to the results of the experiment, it can be noted that the highest indicators of the state of mental operations of analysis and synthesis, comparison and generalization are noted in the aspect of visual material. They are inferior to the indicators of analysis and synthesis of lexical material. The lowest relative to the previous ones are the indicators of phonemic analysis and synthesis. We explain this by the predominance of visual-effective thinking over visual-imaginative, which corresponds to the provisions of L.S. Vygotsky on the peculiarities of the development of children's thinking.

The analysis of the obtained results allowed us to establish that preschoolers with ONR by older age do not reach the necessary level of speech readiness and formation of thought processes. Taking into account the results of the study, a system of correctional and pedagogical work on the formation of speech-thinking activity in older preschoolers with ONR using innovative technologies "Su-Jok therapy" and "Fairy tale therapy" was developed, which is presented in three stages: on the basis of visual material, on the verbal level, on the basis of sound material. According to the pictures, the children were taught methods of comparison, classification; the ability to concentrate on the task, switch from one type of activity to another in individual and group work. The visibility was used in such a way that it allowed an individual approach to the application of each child's abilities.

Here is an approximate list of games using visual material: addition of split pictures; identification of inconsistencies in plot pictures; selection of objects from the general drawing; finding the right element of the drawing; isolation of objects from superimposed images; identification of an extra picture; understanding of multi-stage verbal instructions.

On the basis of verbal material, children learned to reason, to justify their reasoning. The content of the correctional work included speech games and exercises aimed at activating the speech-thinking activity of children, visual-figurative and abstract thinking.

Here is a list of lexical exercises: selection of definitions, epithets, comparisons for the verbal characteristics of the subject; selection of related words, synonyms and antonyms; description

of the signs of the subject according to a given scheme; comparison of concepts, search for signs of similarity and difference; guessing words from the description of actions and signs, inventing similar riddles; identification and explanation of semantic inconsistencies in speech material of different levels; restoration of the sequence of events; propagation of a sentence by adding definitions, verbs and adverbs; restoration of a deformed sentence; making sentences from rearranged ("mixed up") words. The purpose of the third stage of training was the development of speech-thinking activity based on sound material, phonemic perception, complex forms of analysis based on auditory and visual orientations, visual-figurative and verbal-logical thinking, auditory and visual attention.

Games and tasks that contribute to the formation of phonemic processes: isolation of sound from words and its indication in the scheme; naming of a missing sound or syllable; composing words from sounds given in disorder; changing words by changing the places of sounds, reducing the sound composition; identifying differences in the sound composition of words; sequential reading of words along the "chain" of syllables; encoding and decoding of words; recognition of a word by the presence of vowels (consonants) sounds; composing new words from the letters of a given word; composing a chain of words by changing one letter; converting words by changing or adding sounds; composing words from the first (or last) sounds of the named words; solving puzzles, crosswords, mazes.

Purposeful development of speech-thinking skills in the process of coordination and pedagogical work to overcome speech underdevelopment of speech in older preschoolers with ONR leads to positive dynamics, ensures the successful development of speech and non-speech mental processes, a high degree of readiness of preschoolers to learn literacy at school. The proposed system of work reduces the predominance of visual type of thinking and promotes the development of visual-figurative and verbal-logical thinking.

References:

1. Volkovskaya T.N., Yusupova G.H. Psychological assistance to preschoolers with general speech underdevelopment. - M.: Knigolyub, 2004. - 104 p.
2. Leontiev A.A. Language, speech, speech activity. - M.: Enlightenment, 1969. - 214 p.
3. Filicheva T.B., Chirkina G.V. Correctional education and upbringing of 5-year-old children with general speech underdevelopment. - M.: Enlightenment, 1993. - 178 p.